

Exploring Student's Perception on Values Education Program

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ABSTRACT: This study explored education students' perceptions of the Values Education major and how these views affected their choice of course. Using a qualitative, exploratory design and interviews, five main themes were found. Students first saw Values Education as a simple subject, but later understood its deeper meaning involving ethics, psychology, and philosophy. They saw it as important in helping future teachers become responsible and moral individuals, and valued it as much as other majors. Their views became more positive through real-life experiences, mentoring, and classroom learning. Some students chose the major because of personal interest, while others, even if they appreciated it, picked other courses because of practical reasons or beliefs that it was less important. Students suggested promoting the program through success stories, hands-on learning, mentoring, and curriculum changes. The study concludes that students' changing views show the importance of Values Education in shaping good teachers and offer valuable suggestions to enhance the program's impact and relevance.

KEYWORDS: Student Perceptions, Values Education, Exploring, Views, Program Choice, Qualitative Research

CHAPTER I

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Values Education is a process of teaching and learning about the ideals that a society values (Department of Education, Science and Training 2005; Lovat & Toomey 2007; Robb 2008). It aims to influence students' behavior and attitudes. Arweck and Nesbitt describe values-based education as a tool-kit for children, young people, and adults. This tool-kit helps them think about values in their lives. It also assists them in handling relationships and social situations and shapes their attitudes toward others, property, and social structures. In today's educational landscape, values education has received considerable attention. Societies recognize the need to nurture well-rounded individuals who have ethical principles and moral reasoning. This study looks at the perceptions of students in the College of Education, specifically at Leyte Normal University. LNU, known for its commitment to teacher education, is an ideal place to explore how students view values education within their academic experience. The development of values education is affected by various factors, such as globalization, cultural diversity, and changing social norms.

As Tan (2016) points out values education does more than just pass on moral teachings. It involves the development of critical thinking, empathy, and ethical decision-making among students. Understanding the context of values education in the Philippines is important for improving educational practices and encouraging socially responsible citizens. Additionally, the role of educators in shaping students' moral perspectives is crucial. Teachers act as mentors and role models, influencing students' attitudes, beliefs, and values (Maravilla & Tan, 2019). Therefore, uncovering students' views on values education requires examining teaching strategies, classroom dynamics, and teacher-student interactions within the values education program. Values education is essential for developing individuals and fostering a sense of morality and civic responsibility, especially in this generation. As societal values and educational settings change, it is vital to critically assess the perceptions and obstacles that may discourage students from studying this field. According to Dela Cruz (2019), the Philippine Education System offers several academic subjects, including Filipino, English, Mathematics, Science, T.L.E., Araling Panlipunan, MAPEH, and Values Education. Among these, Values Education is often seen as the least important since it is taught only twice a week. Values form an essential part of the human foundation. Teachers significantly contribute to shaping these values for modern students. The Basic Education Curriculum shows that the government is trying to refresh the values of Filipino children in light of the current character crisis.

Understanding students' views, this study also aims to explore broader social influences that might affect attitudes toward values education. Factors such as cultural norms, media representations, and current educational trends can all shape students' perceptions and misunderstandings about this field. By examining these external influences alongside individual beliefs, the research seeks to provide a thorough analysis of the barriers that may prevent students from majoring in values education. Furthermore, the socio-cultural environment of Leyte province adds a unique aspect to the study. The rich cultural heritage and

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socio-economic diversity shape students' worldviews and moral perspectives, highlighting the relationship between local contexts and global influences in forming values (Espina, 2017). By situating the study within the specific socio-cultural context of Leyte Normal University, the research aims to provide insights that are both contextually meaningful and globally relevant.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework for exploring students' perception in Values Education can be grounded in constructivism. **Constructivism**, as proposed by educational theorists like Jean Piaget and Lev Vygotsky, suggests that individuals actively construct their understanding and knowledge of the world through experience and interactions. In the context of this study, students' perception in Values Education can be viewed as dynamic process where they engage with the subject matter, reflect on their own values. This theory is highly applicable to this research title as it provides a lens through which to understand how students develop their values, attitudes, and beliefs within an educational setting.

Kohlberg's stages of moral development theory can also be grounded as one of theoretical framework as it understand students' perceptions of moral issues and provides a structured way to analyze how students reason through ethical dilemmas and identify the level of moral development they are exhibiting in their thinking process.

By exploring students' perception through Kohlberg's stages of moral development and constructivist framework, researchers can delve into the complexities of how Values Education shapes students' perspectives and behaviors, offering valuable insights for educational practice and policy.

Statement of the Problem

This study aims to explore the perceptions of students under College of Education at Leyte Normal University. Specifically it seeks to address the following research questions:

- 1.) What are the perceptions of education students about the Values Education major?
- 2.) How do the perceptions on values education influence education students in choosing the programs?
- 3.) Based on the insights from students perceptions of the Values Education Program, what recommendations can be proposed?

Significance of the Study

This study aims to understand how students, particularly those in the college of education perceive the values education major and how these perceptions influence their decision to pursue it or not. The objectives of this is to identify students perceptions regarding values education, to determine the factors influencing their interest or disinterest in pursuing the program and to explore potential improvements to make the program more appealing and relevant. This study is unique as it not only examines perceptions but also investigates how these views impact students career choices.

This study will have benefits to the following:

To Students. It provides valuable insights into how students perceive with the values imparted in them, illuminating the effectiveness of the current curriculum and teaching methods.

To Educators. This understanding can inform educators on necessary adjustments to enhance the delivery of values education, ensuring its relevance and impact on students' moral and ethical development.

To Society. This study also aims to explore the broader societal influences that may shape attitudes towards values education. Factors such as cultural norms, media portrayals, and prevailing educational trends could all contribute to students' perceptions and misconceptions about the field. By considering these external influences alongside individual beliefs, the research seeks to provide a comprehensive analysis of the barriers that may deter students from choosing values education as their major.

To the Future Researchers. To give idea regarding with this topic and can be serves a good source of accurate and useful information for them.

Definition of Terms

For the purpose of clarity, the researchers operationally defined the following terms:

Values Education Major - is an undergraduate teacher education degree program designed to equip learners with adequate and relevant competencies to teach Values Education. It is a course subject that is being taught from elementary, high school to college mainly with the purpose of teaching morals and ethical decision-making.

Exploring - refers to the investigation, examination, and analysis of various aspects related to the chosen topic, with the aim of gaining deeper insights and understanding.

Perception - is the process of how an individual or group views a phenomenon, and how they process stimuli and incorporate memories and experiences to understand it. It is also the process of using sensory information to understand the world around you.

Scope and Limitation of the Study

The purpose and scope of this study are to better understand the perceptions, views, attitudes of the students under College of Education. Specifically, the Values Education program in a state university in Tacloban City. The main purpose of this is to investigate perceptions of values education program. This study is implemented to undergraduate students who are enrolled under

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the college of education. However, the conclusions of this study are not intended to be generalized to all enrolled students in a state university.

Furthermore, the research will use qualitative method such as interviews to gain in-depth thoughts from students. It is particularly suitable for exploring participants personal experiences which can uncover insights into the subjective meanings they attach to their perceptions. To collect data or information of this study, the researchers will use an interview guide with an open-ended question to the participants. Hence, the study will further examine the various responses of the participants.

CHAPTER II

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

This chapter presents research and literature from both foreign and local researchers that are relevant to the variables included in the study. It focuses on aspects that will contribute to the development of this research.

Biswas (2023) argues that education today should go beyond academics. It needs to instill key values like honesty, empathy, and responsibility, which are essential for making ethical decisions in a fast-paced world. His work highlights how Values Education helps build emotional intelligence, civic duty, and social awareness, preparing students to be responsible citizens. However, the study does not address teacher education, which this research aims to explore. Lickona (1991) defines Values Education as the intentional effort to develop good character through a moral curriculum and a supportive school environment. Halstead and Taylor (2000) back this up by describing Values Education as a way to develop ethical attitudes and personal qualities. Aspin (2007) adds that teaching values allows young people to contribute meaningfully to society. These foundational views shape the theoretical framework of this study, underscoring how education shapes values. Aydın and Akyol Gürler (2012) stress that values are personal and social, rooted in moral foundations. They advocate for universal values that promote harmonious living. Durkheim's concept of moral education and Tezcan's views (1993) further support aligning personal values with societal beliefs, which is important in the Philippine context, where cultural and religious values are deeply woven into education.

Subbalakshmi and Sivakumar looked into student views on how values influence personal development. Their study found that Values Education is key for ethical growth and self-awareness. This connects with the current research's aim to understand students' experiences, especially as they prepare to be future educators. Nucci (2001) introduced the "Domain-Based Moral Education" model, which shows that students engage more when lessons relate to real-life situations, encourage discussion, and include role-playing. Kristjánsson (2013) notes that traditional methods can feel rigid, while student-centered approaches are often more effective. These views inform the teaching methods explored in this research. Arthur et al. (2015) point out that hands-on learning, such as community service and leadership projects, increases the effectiveness of values instruction. Their findings, while primarily based in the UK, apply to teacher education programs aimed at promoting moral development among pre-service teachers. Osguthorpe (2008) examines the moral character of teachers and its impact on students. He claims that teachers act as moral agents and their traits shape the ethical atmosphere in the classroom. This highlights the importance of understanding how education students view their future role in transmitting values. Revell and Arthur (2007) emphasize that teachers' beliefs affect how Values Education is put into practice. Schools that emphasize ethics in teacher training are more likely to inspire students' interest in the Values Education major. Eccles and Wigfield (2002) also mention that factors like student motivation, identity, and emotions significantly influence academic and career choices, including the decision to pursue Values Education. Berkowitz and Bier (2005), Narvaez and Lapsley (2005, 2006), and Arthur (2010) stress the value of teaching strategies like character modeling, reflective practice, and service-learning. These methods encourage deeper engagement with values and support students' identity development, which is crucial for future educators. Cohen (1995) argues that school culture and parental involvement are vital for sustaining Values Education. This implies that values need to be reinforced in both school and the wider community. These insights contextualize the study within Filipino society, where education is a collective responsibility.

The uniqueness of this study stems from its primary goal to provide new insights that significantly differ from earlier research related to our topic, particularly since many previous studies come from the 1990s. This research delves deeper into students' perceptions of the Values Education Program, aiming to reveal not just their opinions but also the motivations and influences that shape them. Unlike earlier studies that looked at Values Education broadly, this one specifically examines students in the college of education, who have a distinct role as future educators. It also stands out because it can be replicated in other institutions for comparison. However, it still follows established research methods, theories, and data analysis strategies, similar to past studies. Its main aim aligns with the stated problem: to understand why students choose to pursue or overlook Values Education, offering new insights while remaining rooted in established academic methods.

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CHAPTER III

METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents the methodology that will be used to undertake this study. This include the research design, research participant, locale of the study, sample and sampling technique, research instrument used, data gathering procedure, data analysis, and ethical considerations.

Research Design

This study adopts a qualitative research design to explore student's perceptions of the Values Education Program under the College of Education. A qualitative approach is suitable for this study as it allows an in-depth understanding of participants experiences, thoughts, and attitudes. According to Creswell (2014), qualitative research is ideal for exploring and interpreting complex social phenomena, especially when the goal is to derive meanings rather than quantify data.

Exploratory methodology will be utilized. This research approach used to investigate topics that are not yet well understood, allowing researchers to gain deeper insights into participants perceptions, experiences, and viewpoints. It is particularly effective for studying perceptions of values education program, as it allows for a thorough exploration of how individuals understand and experience its influence on their personal choices and moral growth. As noted by Stebbins (2001) in Exploratory Research in the Social Science, this method is valuable for examining human behaviors and perceptions, especially in areas with limited prior studies.

Research Participant

The participants of this study are undergraduate students enrolled from different programs under the college of education in one of the Universities of Tacloban City. These programs include Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEED), Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED), and other related courses except those students enrolled under the College of Arts and Sciences, College of Management and Entrepreneurship and so as students who are not studying in Leyte Normal University. The selection of participants from the various programs of education provides a comprehensive understanding of how the Values Education Program is perceived across different academic tracks. A total of twenty (20) students are selected for this study. According to Guest, Bunce, and Johnson (2006) in How Many Interviews Are Enough? found that data saturation often occurs within the first 12 to 20 interviews, making 20 participants an appropriate number for such a study. This approach ensures that the study captures meaningful insights while maintaining feasibility in data collection and analysis.

Locale of the Study

The study will be conducted in one of the universities at Tacloban City, Leyte. This institution is selected for known as it's excellence in education and a leading university of education in Eastern Visayas. This study is implemented to undergraduate students who are enrolled under the college of education. This study aims to explore student's perceptions of the Values Education program as its central focus. The research study is implemented inside the premises of the state university, in a classroom that was clean and available, well-ventilated, and equipped with enough chairs for all participating students. This setting provided an ideal environment for the study, helping the researchers gain insights into how students perceive the Values Education program.

Sample and Sampling Technique

The study will be utilizing non-probability sampling technique, particularly the purposive sampling. Purposive sampling, also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling (Crossman, 2020). In this case, the researcher will purposefully select 20 students who have experienced the values education subject or the ESP during their grade school and secondary level ensuring that they can provide relevant and insightful perceptions about Values Education Program. Within purposive sampling, the researcher has set the following inclusion criteria. First, the participants must be students of a state university. Second, they must be enrolled in a program within the College of Education. Lastly, they must have prior experience with the Values Education/ESP subject during their grade school and secondary levels.

Furthermore, students from the College of Arts and Sciences (CAS) and the College of Management and Entrepreneurship (CME) are excluded from this study. Since they are not enrolled in the College of Education they may not have the same academic exposure or direct engagement with the Values Education Program as education students. Therefore, their perspectives and perceptions may not align with the study's objectives, which focus on students specializing in education related fields.

Research Instrument Used

The main instrument in this study is interview. The researchers used interview guide questions which includes brief information on the purpose of the study. The interview guide consists of open-ended questions to provide learners the scope to reflect and review from their different perceptions or perspectives about values education program. This interview guide contains three parts. First is the information Sheet which includes the participants name (optional), date, time started, time ended, mobile number, and the things that the researchers need to do before the interview will start. Secondly, the questions to the participants. Lastly, the

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closing statements where includes asking the participants if they would like to add or have a clarifications regarding the interview and short thankyou message for giving their time and participation of this study .

Data collection will be conducted in stages using informal and conversational interviews. This method creates a more relaxed environment, making participants feel comfortable sharing their genuine opinions. Additionally, this approach allows the researchers to adjust their questions based on participants' responses, leading to a deeper exploration of their thoughts and perceptions. This technique ensures a more natural flow of discussion, helping to uncover meaningful insights about the values education program.

Data Gathering Procedure

The data gathering procedure will involve several steps to ensure the collection of comprehensive and reliable information from the participant. The researchers will carry out the following steps in gathering the needed data. Prior to starting the data collection, a consent letter will be given to the selected participants of the study. Once the participants have given their consent, they will be told of the study's goals, the method of data collection, including the day and time of the data collection, and the date on which the intervention will be implemented. Each interview session will be audio recorded. The consent of participants will be given first to ensure accurate data capture. Following the interviews, the recordings will be transcribed verbatim to facilitate data analysis and will be reviewed for completeness and consistency before being categorized for analysis. Throughout the data gathering process, ethical considerations will be crucial, ensuring the rights and welfare of the participants are respected.

Data Analysis

The researchers will analyze the responses of the participants from the undergraduate students enrolled within the program of college of education using thematic analysis. The responses will be grouped together based on their commonalities and will be given a code to make it easy to recognize each one. Based on the tabulation of responses, the data will summarize and, the findings of this research. The responses provided by the participants will be regarded as the most important factor in resolving the study's problem, which is "Exploring Student's Perception on Values Education Program". The processes of thematic analysis as they are outlined by Braun and Clarke (2006) enable both a systematic way of viewing and the "coding" of qualitative data. According to Braun and Clarke (2006), the several stages of the thematic analysis used in the current study are as follows. First, data familiarization is the process of reviewing and rereading the data while transcribing it and making initial notes. For each transcript, the key points were underlined and noted. Second, composing the initial codes entails "gathering data pertinent to each code, systematically coding important elements of the data across the full data collection" (Braun & Clarke, 2006, p. 87). Features were coded during translation and transcription as brief phrases or keywords that referred to a particular concept. To maintain track of the condensed information, memos were written down. Third, finding patterns in the data: "Collecting codes into possible themes, compiling all information pertinent to each possible theme" (Braun & Clarke, 2006, p. 87). To keep the number of codes and group them into recognizable themes, the data were reviewed and reread numerous times in this cycle. Following analysis, the codes were categorized into main themes, which are described in the following section. Fourth, a thematic map of the analysis is created by evaluating the topics in connection to the coded extracts at the first level and the complete data set at the second level (Braun & Clarke, 2006, p. 87). To verify the codes, the entire interview data set was read again. Thematic maps were created that were utilized to identify patterns in the data. Fifth, creating the report: "The final analysis; selection of vivid, captivating extract examples, the final analysis of selected extracts, the analysis to their search question and literature, producing a scholarly report of the analysis" (Braun & Clarke, 2006, p. 87). To demonstrate the outcomes both as statements in the form of ideas and sentiments and as graphic representations produced utilizing linkages between codes, some key statements/features reflecting the data were retrieved.

Ethical Considerations

The researchers ensures that the safety of the participants in conducting the study should be well accommodated. All the responses of the participants before, during, and after the interview acquires confidentiality for its privacy standards. On the other hand, the researchers will create formal letter as a letter consent that will be sent to the participants to ask their approval for the survey and interview process. The letters primary consent includes primary informations such as the research topic and it's purposes. Hence, this is part of their right as the respondents of the said study. The following are considered as part of ensuring the privacy and safety of the participants included in this study:

Informed Consent

Prior to participating in the research, it is our responsibility to make sure that the participants are fully informed about the study, its purpose, potential risks, and benefits. They should know that their participation is voluntary and that they can withdraw at any time without repercussions.

Privacy and confidentiality

Their privacy is of utmost importance to us. All the information they provide will be handled with strict confidentiality. No

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personally identifying information (such as the name, school ID, or contact details) will be collected. The responses will be recorded anonymously and stored in secure, password-protected files accessible only to the research team. The data will be used solely for academic purposes, and results will be presented in aggregated form to ensure that no individual participant can be identified. Additionally, any identifying details that they might accidentally share will be removed before analysis. We assure each of them that participation in this study is entirely voluntary. They have the right to withdraw at any point without any negative consequences. Their willingness to participate is highly appreciated, and their insights will play a vital role in advancing knowledge and understanding in this area.

Risk

Participating in this study may cause discomfort in sharing personal opinions or emotional distress if sensitive topics are discussed. There may also be concerns about confidentiality. To minimize these, participants can skip questions or withdraw at any time without obligation.

Beneficence & non-maleficence

In this research, we have an obligation to maximize benefits and minimize potential harm to the participants. This involves weighing the potential societal benefits of the research against any potential harm it may cause to the participants. Participants will have the opportunity to share their insights, helping improve the Values Education Program. They will also receive snacks as a token of appreciation. Additionally, their contributions may help refine teaching strategies, making values education more effective and empowering students to shape educational practices.

Autonomy Respect

A. Participants are treated with respect and their autonomy are upheld. As researchers, we avoid coercion or manipulation and ensure that participants have the freedom to make their own decisions regarding participation.

COI - Conflict of Interest

In this research, we disclose any potential conflicts of interest that could compromise the integrity of the research or its outcomes. This is essential for maintaining transparency and trust in the research process.

Data Manipulation

Data manipulation will be avoided to uphold the accuracy and integrity of the research findings. Rigorous analysis and interpretation of the data will be conducted to prevent distortion or misrepresentation.

Intellectual Property

Intellectual property rights will be respected through proper citation and acknowledgment of existing work or ideas. Plans for publication or sharing of the research findings will adhere to ethical guidelines.

Continuing Monitoring & Reflection

The research will be continuously monitored and reflected upon to identify and address any potential ethical concerns that may arise during the study, ensuring the well-being and rights of the participants.

Research Dissemination

The plan for disseminating the research findings will prioritize accuracy and responsibility. After dissemination, the research findings may be considered for publication in academic journals or institutional repositories to contribute to future studies.

CHAPTER IV

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the ideas and opinions of students about the Values Education Program using their answers gathered from open-ended interviews. It uses thematic analysis to organize their responses into clear themes that explain how they view the program, what influences their decision to take it or not, and what improvements they suggest. The chapter highlights their reasons for whether choosing the course or not, their experiences, and the kind of support they believe is needed. Overall, it gives a simple and deeper understanding of how students from the college of education see the Values Education major and how it can be improved for future learners.

The perceptions of education students about the Values Education major are encapsulated into themes and thematic statements as presented in Table 1.

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Table 1. Perceptions about Values Education Major

Themes	Thematic Statements
Theme 1. Evolving Understanding of Values Education	<p>Many students initially viewed Values Education as a simple subject centered around basic moral lessons but later recognized its deeper role in personal and societal development.</p> <p><i>"At first, I thought Values Education was just about teaching right and wrong... It seemed simple and not that serious."</i> – Student C</p> <p><i>"My initial thought about values education is that this major is all about learning how to teach people good manner or saying po and opo."</i> – Student H</p> <p>However, this perception changed over time as they encountered more complex topics.</p> <p><i>"Now I see it as a complex and meaningful course... it takes patience, understanding, and a lot of heart."</i> – Student C</p> <p><i>"I realized it's challenging and meaningful."</i> – Student P</p> <p><i>"I didn't know it involves deep discussions on ethics, human behavior, and moral development."</i> – Student P</p> <p><i>"It delves into the psychology of life and explores various philosophies about human existence."</i> – Student O</p>
Theme 2: Values Education Shapes Morally Responsible Educators	<p>Respondents consistently emphasized the importance of Values Education in shaping teachers who serve as ethical role models and moral guides.</p> <p><i>"Teachers are not just there to teach facts. They're also role models."</i> – Student I</p> <p><i>"Values Education equips them with the tools to instill strong moral principles in their students."</i> – Student A</p> <p><i>"It helps them become good role models... and create a safe and caring classroom."</i> – Student B</p> <p><i>"Values Education make future teachers ready, like spiritually ready when they go into the field."</i> – Student G</p>
Theme 3: Equal Importance with Other Majors	<p>Many students felt that Values Education is just as important as academic majors like Math, Science, or English.</p> <p><i>"Without values, knowledge is useless."</i> – Student C</p> <p><i>"A school needs both knowledge and values."</i> – Student B</p> <p><i>"Values Education helps create not only smart but also kind and responsible individuals."</i> – Student B</p> <p><i>"There is no such thing as superiority or inferiority. So, yes!"</i> – Student K</p> <p><i>"Yes, but it's often overlooked."</i> – Student S</p>
Theme 4: Complexity Beneath the Surface	<p>While Values Education may appear simple to outsiders, students described it as a complex and intellectually demanding course.</p> <p><i>"It's not just about memorizing rules, but understanding their application."</i> – Student A</p> <p><i>"It requires critical thinking, self-reflection, and practical application."</i> – Student F</p> <p><i>"People have different beliefs, cultures, and experiences... guiding without judging is hard."</i> – Student B</p> <p><i>"We deal with emotional, spiritual, and psychological aspects of students."</i> – Student R</p>
Theme 5: Perceptions Shift Through Exposure and Experience	<p>Perceptions of the Values Education major have changed over time for many students due to education, personal experiences, and peer influence.</p> <p><i>"I viewed it as a less practical field... now my appreciation grew significantly."</i> – Student A</p> <p><i>"My understanding has deepened over time as I've learned more about its multifaceted nature."</i> – Student M</p> <p><i>"After hearing perspectives of my friends taking the course, I realized how deep and meaningful the subject really is."</i> – Student N</p> <p><i>"Talking to educators and seeing how values affect real-life situations made me appreciate it more."</i> – Student I</p>

The perceptions of education students about the Values Education major are summarized into five main themes. First, students' understanding evolved from thinking it was a simple subject about basic manners to recognizing its deeper importance in personal and societal growth. They later appreciated that it involves complex topics like ethics, psychology, and philosophy. Second, they viewed Values Education as a way to shape morally responsible teachers who can be role models and build caring, inclusive classrooms. Third, students believed that Values Education is equally important as other majors, balancing academic knowledge with moral and character development. Fourth, they recognized the complexity of the course, highlighting the need for critical thinking, emotional awareness, and understanding of diverse cultures and beliefs. Lastly, students' perceptions shifted as they gained more exposure to the subject, learned from mentors and classmates, and connected the lessons to real-life experiences. These insights show that Values Education is not just about teaching right and wrong it plays a vital role in shaping future educators with both heart and mind.

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Table 2. Influence of Perceptions on Students' Choice of Program

Themes	Thematic Statements
<p>Theme 1. Influence of Personal Perception on Career Direction</p> <p>1.1 Inspired by the Transformative Role of Values Education</p>	<p>Some students, while not majoring in Values Education, shared that their positive views of the program influenced them to pursue related education programs. They acknowledged Values Education's critical role in shaping well-rounded individuals and contributing to society.</p> <p>"Although I did not pursue Val.Ed, my positive perception of its importance in shaping individuals and its impact on society strongly influenced my decision to pursue a related field in education." – Student A</p> <p>"My perception of Values Education influenced my choice of major by helping me see its true importance. I realized being a teacher is not just about teaching subjects, but also shaping students' character." – Student B</p> <p>"My perception of Values Education influenced my choice of major by helping me realize the importance of shaping not just minds, but also hearts and character." – Student E</p> <p>These responses show that Values Education is seen not only as a subject but also as a foundation for responsible teaching and moral guidance.</p>
<p>1.2 Alignment with Personal Passion and Values</p>	<p>A few students mentioned that they chose Values Education because it aligned with their passion for influencing others positively and promoting good values.</p> <p>"I am passionate in influencing people by having them imposing 'good' values. Thus, Values Education major aligned with this passion of mine." – Student D</p> <p>"It confirmed my decision to take it as a major." – Student R</p> <p>Their choice of major was guided by an internal desire to model and teach values, reflecting a strong identification with the program's goals.</p>
<p>1.3 Emotional and Self-Discovery Growth</p>	<p>Some respondents were initially unaware of the program's depth but later appreciated its emotional and personal development aspects.</p> <p>"I chose this major because I thought it was easier than Science... But now, I am thankful I picked this course. It helped me grow and understand myself better." – Student C</p> <p>"Values Education can spark a passion for roles in teaching. It can also shape the approach to decision-making and ethical considerations in any profession." – Student F</p> <p>These insights reveal that for some students, their perception of the program evolved over time as they experienced personal growth through the course.</p>
<p>Theme 2. Lack of Direct Influence Despite Acknowledging Its Importance</p> <p>2.1 Chose Different Majors Based on Interest or Practicality</p>	<p>Many students admitted that their choice of major was not influenced by Values Education, even if they acknowledged its value.</p> <p>"I saw Values Education as important, but it does not influence my choice of major." – Student I</p> <p>"It didn't influence me much, but I admire those who chose it." – Student S</p> <p>"Honestly, it did not influence my choice of major." – Student N</p> <p>"To be honest, it didn't play the most part of my choice of major." – Student K</p> <p>This theme highlights how personal interest, career goals, or other factors often outweigh students' perceptions of Values Education when choosing a major.</p>
<p>2.2 External or Practical Factors as Deciding Influence</p>	<p>Several respondents said that their decision was based more on employment opportunities, interests, or available courses rather than the influence of Values Education.</p> <p>"I didn't choose it, but it made me more respectful towards my friends who did. I now see how essential their role is in developing moral character." – Student P</p> <p>"I felt more connected to teaching young kids." – Student T</p> <p>"My passion for writing and reading led me to English." – Student Q</p> <p>"I chose a different major that aligned more with my personal interests and strengths which is Filipino." – Student N</p> <p>This indicates that while students respect the field of Values Education, their choice of program was more influenced by personal goals or passions.</p>

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Theme 3. Influence of Social Environment and Reputation	<p>Concerns about future job prospects, earning potential, and societal recognition discouraged some students from choosing Values Education despite acknowledging its worth.</p> <p>“Concerns about limited career options and perceived lack of practical application led me to choose a different major.” – Student A</p>
3.1 Perceived Career Limitations and Societal Views	<p>“I had doubts whether I’d have good job opportunities if I chose it.” – Student I</p> <p>“Some students think it’s just common sense or something anyone can teach.” – Student T</p> <p>This suggests that perceptions of the major’s societal value strongly influence students’ decision-making process.</p>
3.2 Misconceptions About the Program	<p>Some students mentioned that misconceptions, such as the idea that Values Education is an “easy” or “boring” course, affected their or their peers' perception and ultimately their decision.</p> <p>“Many think it only talks about basic rules, but it also helps students understand deeper topics like respect, empathy, and making good choices.” – Student B</p> <p>“Many students think this course is easy. They say it’s only about respect and good manners. But they don’t know how deep and emotional it gets.” – Student C</p> <p>“Some think it’s an ‘easy major’ or it’s boring.” – Student P</p> <p>These statements reflect how negative or shallow impressions can impact a student's willingness to explore the course further.</p>

The perceptions of education students about the Values Education major are encapsulated into themes and thematic statements, as presented in Table 2. The findings reveal that for some students, positive views about the Values Education program influenced their career paths by aligning with their personal passion and desire to become morally responsible educators. These students saw the program as a meaningful and transformative field that helps shape both character and society. Others experienced personal growth after entering the program, which further deepened their commitment to it. However, many students chose different majors despite acknowledging the importance of Values Education. Their decisions were often guided by interests, career practicality, or the belief that other fields offered better job opportunities. Social perceptions and misconceptions about the program such as it being “easy” or “less important” also played a role in discouraging students from choosing it. This shows that while Values Education is respected, its influence on students’ program choices varies depending on personal goals, practical considerations, and societal attitudes.

Table 3. Recommendations Based on Students’ Perceptions of the Values Education Program

Themes	Thematic Statements
Theme 1: Help Students Understand the Program Better	<p>Many students said that they and others may not fully understand what the Values Education major is. They believe that more effort should be made to explain the course clearly.</p> <p><i>“Real stories can help others understand the course better.” - Student C</i></p> <p><i>“Success stories and real-life applications will help students understand.” - Student A</i></p> <p><i>“It’s how well the course is promoted in schools.” - Student T</i></p> <p><i>“Lack of awareness can be a barrier.” - Student S</i></p>
Theme 2: Provide More Practical and Hands-On Experiences	<p>Students said they would like the course to include more real-life activities like community service, classroom teaching, and projects.</p> <p><i>“Students will benefit from real-life experiences like internships.” - Student E</i></p> <p><i>“Fieldwork and hands-on teaching will help more students get interested.” - Student I</i></p> <p><i>“Classroom observations and values formation projects will help.” - Student T</i></p> <p><i>“Community-based projects and leadership training can make the course more attractive.” -Student O</i></p>
Theme 3: Give More Support to Students	<p>Students said they need emotional, academic, and career support while taking the Values Education major.</p> <p><i>“Students need mentors and career counseling.” - Student A</i></p> <p><i>“They need guidance to explore their future jobs.” - Student F</i></p> <p><i>“The course is not just about the brain, but also the heart.” - Student C</i></p> <p><i>“They need support because the course deals with real and sometimes heavy issues.” - Student I</i></p>
Theme 4: Improve the Curriculum and Show Career Opportunities	<p>Students believe that the program can be improved by updating the lessons and clearly showing possible jobs after graduation.</p> <p><i>“Add psychology subjects it helps understand behavior better.” - Student C</i></p> <p><i>“Include leadership and mental health topics.” - Student R</i></p> <p><i>“Highlight different job opportunities.” - Student A</i></p> <p><i>“Show success stories from Values Education graduates.” - Student N</i></p>

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Theme 5: Encourage Students to Reflect and Find Purpose	Students shared that future Values Education students should be reminded about the deeper purpose of the course. <i>"It's more than just learning right from wrong." - Student O</i> <i>"It will help you live with meaning and purpose." - Student C</i> <i>"If you really want to help others, go for it." - Student I</i> <i>"Be open-minded and patient. It's a deeply fulfilling path." - Student T</i>
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The recommendations provided by the students regarding the Values Education program are grouped into major themes based on their insights and experiences. These suggestions are aimed at improving how the program is understood, how students are supported, and how the course can be made more engaging and relevant to real-life teaching. First, students emphasized the importance of helping others understand the true essence of the Values Education major, suggesting the use of real-life stories from graduates and improved program promotion in schools. Second, they recommended providing more practical and hands-on experiences such as internships, outreach activities, and classroom observations to enhance learning and attract more students. Third, they pointed out the need for stronger support systems, including mentoring, career counseling, and emotional guidance, due to the moral and psychological depth of the course. Fourth, students called for curriculum improvements, including the addition of subjects like psychology, leadership, and mental health, along with clearer pathways to possible careers after graduation. Lastly, students encouraged future enrollees to reflect on the purpose and passion required for taking the course. They believe that understanding the deeper meaning of Values Education will help students connect with it on a personal level and find fulfillment in their future roles as educators. These findings provide actionable insights for enhancing the appeal and effectiveness of the Values Education program.

CHAPTER V

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter presents a summary of the findings, conclusions based on the data analysis, and recommendations.

A. Summary

The findings of the study were summarized according to the statement of the problems stated in Chapter I.

Perceptions of education students about Values Education Major

- Evolving Understanding of Values Education
- Values Education Shapes Morally Responsible Educators
- Equal Importance with Other Majors
- Complexity Beneath the Surface
- Perceptions Shift Through Exposure and Experience

How do the perceptions on values education influence education students in choosing the programs include:

- Influence of Personal Perception on Career Direction
 - 1.1 Inspired by the Transformative Role of Values Education
 - 1.2 Alignment with Personal Passion and Values
 - 1.3 Emotional and Self-Discovery Growth
- Lack of Direct Influence Despite Acknowledging Its Importance
 - 2.1 Chose Different Majors Based on Interest or Practicality
 - 2.2 External or Practical Factors as Deciding Influence
- Influence of Social Environment and Reputation
 - 3.1 Perceived Career Limitations and Societal Views
 - 3.2 Misconceptions About the Program

Recommendations Based on Students' Perceptions of the Values Education Program

- Help Students Understand the Program Better
- Provide More Practical and Hands-On Experiences
- Give More Support to Students
- Improve the Curriculum and Show Career Opportunities
- Encourage Students to Reflect and Find Purpose

B. Conclusions

This study on students' views of the Values Education Program offers important insights into how education students perceive and respond to the course. The findings indicate that students' views have shifted. They now see Values Education not just as a basic subject about good manners but as a complex and transformative force in shaping character, critical thinking, and moral responsibility. The program is increasingly seen as essential for developing ethical educators and holds equal importance to other academic majors. While some students chose different specializations due to practical, personal, or social reasons, many

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recognized the value of Values Education in fostering both intellectual and emotional intelligence. Their perspectives highlighted that, although often underestimated, the course demands deep reflection, cultural awareness, and psychological insight.

Additionally, students made clear and actionable suggestions for improving the program. They recommended better promotion, more real-life experiences, emotional support, curriculum improvements, and guidance on career options. They also stressed the need for future students to think about the purpose of the course and choose it based on genuine passion and a wish to inspire others. Overall, this study shows that the Values Education program plays a crucial role in teacher education. It nurtures capable future educators and contributes to the moral and social fabric of society. With increased awareness, support, and curriculum development, the program can attract more students and enhance its impact in education.

C. Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations can be made:

1. Improve Awareness and Promotion of the Program

Schools should create better strategies to introduce and explain the Values Education major to students. This can include orientation sessions, promotional materials, and talks from graduates who can share their real experiences and how the program impacted their careers.

2. Add More Practical and Hands-On Learning

The curriculum should feature more experiential activities, such as community outreach programs, classroom observations, internships, and values-based projects. These experiences will help students apply theoretical knowledge in real situations, making the subject more engaging and relevant.

3. Strengthen Emotional, Academic, and Career Support

Students in the Values Education major should have access to counseling services, mentorship programs, and academic advising. These support systems can help them cope with the emotional and moral challenges of the course while preparing for their future careers.

4. Update and Broaden the Curriculum

The program should include additional subjects such as psychology, leadership, and mental health education. These topics will enhance students' understanding of human behavior and better equip them to meet diverse classroom needs.

5. Clarify Career Pathways

Clear information about career opportunities for Values Education graduates should be provided. Highlighting success stories and job options can help counter the belief that the course has limited job prospects.

6. Promote Reflection and Purpose-Driven Enrollment

Encourage prospective students to consider their motivations and goals when choosing the program. Teachers and counselors should help students grasp the purpose of Values Education and inspire those who genuinely want to be moral leaders and educators.

7. Address Misconceptions about the Course

Schools should actively challenge the idea that Values Education is an "easy" or "less important" major. Emphasizing its academic rigor and emotional depth will elevate its status and encourage more students to see it as a valuable specialization.

These recommendations aim to strengthen the Values Education program by making it more visible, relevant, and supportive. This approach will ultimately cultivate future educators who are not only competent but also compassionate, ethical, and socially responsible.

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